

RAPTURE TO REVULSION: UNRAVELLING THE MYTHS OF FEAR AND LOATHING IN THE ROMANTIC LITERATURE

Yumna Khatoon^{*1}, Muhammad Mamnoon Akhter²,
Muhammad Hamza Iqbal³^{*1}Lecturer Department of English, Federal Urdu University Arts Science & Technology, Karachi, Pakistan.²Professor, Department of English, Jinnah University of Women, Karachi, Pakistan³B.Sc. Information Technology, Bahria University Karachi, Pakistan.¹yumna.khatoon@fuuast.edu.pk, ²amammedmamnoon@gmail.com, ³hamza_iqbal007@hotmail.comDOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15761414>**Keywords**Fear Loathing Expressionism
Occultism Supernaturalism
Gothicism.**Article History**

Received on 19 May 2025

Accepted on 19 June 2025

Published on 28 June 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Yumna Khatoon

Abstract

In the annals of history, the Romantic era (1798-1837) is a time of socio-political upheaval and chaos ignited by the Industrial Revolution (1760-1830s), French Revolution (1789-1799), and Napoleonic Wars (1803-1815). The Romantic period is known as the Reign of Terror which grappled the profound shifts of changing world from revolutionary fervor to tyrannical despotism. The elements such as the Law of Suspects (1793-1794), the Revolutionary Tribunals (1792-1794) and executionary instrument the Guillotine; represented a system of terror instilled fear in populace that morphed into loathing. The major societal disorder, political instability and violent conflicts shaped the Romantic sensibility of Romantic writers who evoked in their literary contributions the elements of macabre, supernatural, uncanny, alienation and the insignificance of humanity in the face of cosmos. The Romantic Literature provided a gateway to explore the darker abyss and recesses of human psyche and disintegration of self. The objective of research is to provide the critique to the societal norms and darker impulses lurking beneath the age of Romanticism. The research is qualitative in approach employing textual analysis in detail. The research deeply delves into the theories of Postcolonialism, Spermatic Economy and Degeneration to get the desired outcome. The research concludes at the close considering of complex interplay of intellectual dissatisfaction on logic and universal principles that neglected cries for liberty, equality and fraternity.

INTRODUCTION

Fuson Wang in his work *The Historicist Turn of Romantic-Era Disability Studies* stated that, "The Romantic era represents a transitional moment between Enlightenment yearning for universal humanism and the Victorian codification of social mores, its sits between two restrictive movements to classify the human against the inhuman and the normal against the abnormal" (84).

The Romantic era is a genre covering wide fields in literature, art and music arises from sense of dynamism and progressivism created by Proto-Romantic Movement; Strum and Drang in German Literature between 1760-1780. The term Strum and Drang first appeared in play *Klinger* by Friedrich Maxmillan unfolding setbacks of American Revolt fused with violent expressions and extols individuality and subjectivity. Thus, expressionism, individualism

and subjectivity with intensification of feelings and emotions became the hall mark of Romantic Literature. Romance for Romantic writers in English Literature is structured as yearning to connect with something existed outside their selves born between the passions of desire and loss, reach and grasp that laid the foundation for stylistic themes and settings for Romantic narratives that thrive in contemporary behavior. The Romantic Movement is primarily a European Phenomenon associated with toil and turmoil Romantics faced at individual and collective level during French Revolution (1789-1795), Napoleonic Wars (1803-1815) and American Revolution (1775-1783). The British Reform Movement became the platform to shape and develop French and American ideologies. The French rebelled against monarchy and irreflexible older orders while Americans rebelled against the British colonialism and taxation and paved the way for Romantic anxiety and obsession towards reach and grasp motif. The age valorized obsession in grand narratives of war and blood, exotic paradigm and sense of otherness, neurotic anxiety and supernaturalism, scientific rationalism and spirituality, deformed bodies and freakishness and western imperialism and globalized domesticity in order to acknowledge own deviant behavior and limitations to loath from these experiences to attain order, peace and harmony in distorted society.

The term fear and loathing became the counterculture sensation in the Romantic literature delivered through unforgettable and revolutionary literary styles of the Romantic writers. The writers used the bizarre and excessive landscape as a backdrop to explore the themes of disillusionment, paranoia and search for meaning in a decadent and chaotic world. Fear and loathing offered a sharp critique of visual chaos and social commentary of the period intertwined with the movement's core tenets. Philosophers across history have grappled with the definition of fear revealing evolving perspectives shaped by the changing world. Aristotle in his Rhetoric and Nicomachean Ethics defined fear as, "a pain or disturbance due to mental picture of some destructive evil that has potential to inflict significant pain" (Taylor 1818). Stoic philosopher Epictetus in Enchiridion viewed fear as, "Fear is seen as irrational emotion that enslaves us. It prevents us exercising reason. We tend to fear things

that are not within our power to control such as opinions of others, death and poverty. We desire to avoid these things and recognize our lack of complete control over them, fear arises" (Higginson 1955). Marcus Aurelius in Meditations defines fear as, "fear is a mental disturbance that hinders virtue and tranquility" (2018). Seneca in his essay On Anger elaborated the term as, "fear is not simply an instinct but a product of our judgements and opinions about potential future harm. We suffer more in imagination than in reality. The remedy of fear lies in reason, courage, and facing what we dread" (Kaster 2010). Thomas Hobbes in Leviathan offered a more political and psychological perspective on fear as, "fear is a tool for social control. The sovereign power legitimately uses fear of punishment to enforce laws...war of all against all" (2017). Rene Descartes in his work Passions of the Soul illustrated that, "fear is one of the six primitive passions caused by the mind's perception that something is evil or will cause the soul harm, leading the body to prepare for action" (1989). Baruch Spinoza in his literary contribution Ethics ponders over the term fear as, "fear arises from anxiety caused by doubt associated with a transition to a lesser state of perfection or power" (2005). Existentialist philosopher, Jean Paul Sartre in his literary icon Existentialism and Humanism explored fear as, "a response to freedom and responsibility...the burden of making choices and creating own values in a meaningless universe leads to fear" (2007). The contemporary understanding of fear moves beyond the simple 'fight-or-flight' response. It acknowledges the intricate interplay between our biology, cognitive interpretations, and social and cultural environments individuals inhabit. Fear is universal emotional experience associated with immediate, automatic response to a perceived threat or danger. Psychologically fear serves as an alarm system alerting us to potential harm and preparing us to respond effectively. Neuroscience has identified key brain regions involved in processing fear notably 'amygdala'. The amygdala initiates the psychological changes associated with fear-conditioning leading to fear-response upon encountering the danger or threat. The sociolinguistics and cultural theorists highlighted how fear is generated, kept and maintained by socio-cultural contexts. Within social contexts fear amplified moral panics where certain groups,

community or tyranny of majority disseminated intense disorder, and anarchy due to difference in ideological, historical and political dynamics. In Romantic literature, fear and loathing are powerful undercurrents intertwined into one another. Loathing is defined as an intense, pervasive, visceral emotional response of extreme disgust, detestation directed towards societal constraints, injustice, inequality, and discrimination for its unnatural existence and horrifying appearance perceived as fundamentally repugnant, morally corrupt and utterly beyond redemption. The sense of fear is seen as moral failure to acknowledge shared humanity and generates sense of loathing which is dehumanizing and demoralizing in nature. Loathing acts as a powerful catalyst for social fragmentation and conflict. It fuels 'us vs. them' narratives making social cohesion extremely difficult. The paper undertakes the task to decipher the myths of 'fear and loathing' in multiple narratives with understanding the nature, causes and consequences of fear and loathing as a central percept of the current philosophical inquiry.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Victor Hugo in preface to *Hernani* wrote that, "Romanticism was nothing more than liberalism in literature" (1830). The statement is provocative to the reflection of liberal ideas in Romantic literature. The Romantic movement profoundly emphasized on power of individual creativity and quest for self-expression. The Romantic writers celebrated the heroic individual unburdened by conventions challenging the status quo advocating for egalitarian society. The Romantics laid the ground work for ideas of universal human rights asserting equality and shared human values. They were keen to address the plight of society like social injustice, inequality, oppression, violence, and moral debasement reflecting the liberal concerns for human dignity. They employed a wide variety of literary techniques as a potent symbolic tool of allegory in the broader project of artistic and intellectual liberation. Their fascination with rebels, outsiders, outcast, grotesque and abject elements mirrored a concern for those who are marginalized, oppressed, humiliated, discriminated and disillusioned by society. The Romantic period is a direct reaction to historical happenings of the French Revolution and the

Napoleonic Wars. The French Revolution started with great zealous events such as: the summoning of the Estates-General (1789), declaration of National Assembly for commoners (1789), storming of the Bastille (1789) and Tennis Court Oath (1789) leading to political and radical changes. The French Revolution brought Napoleon Bonaparte (1769-1821) to power as First Counsel. William Wordsworth describes the euphoria and optimism of French Revolution in *The Prelude* (1850) as, Bliss was it in that dawn to be alive,

But to be young was very heaven!

The lines captured the immense hope and excitement that swept across Europe for liberty, equality and fraternity. While Napoleon's rise did bring an end to monarchy but his subsequent move to establish himself as emperor and his expansionist policies ultimately formed authoritarian rule. This shift from revolutionary fervor to imperial regime can be seen as deviation from enchantment to disenchantment. The Napoleonic Wars (1803-1815) were series of conflict stemmed from the French Revolutionary Wars (1792-1802) pitted the French Empire against European powers particularly Great Britain, Prussia, Russia and Austria. The other monarchical powers of Europe; Great Britain, Prussia, Russia and Austria were inherently hostile to revolutionary France from outset. They feared the spread of republicans and nationalist ideas that could destabilize their regimes. Therefore, the Europeans powers formed coalitions (First, Second, Third, Fourth, Fifth, Sixth and Seventh) to defeat France. The Napoleonic Wars were nearly 23 years of continuous conflict in Europe in which 2,500,000 military and 1000,000 civilians were killed.

Napoleon Bonaparte as a general risen from the ranks as military genius, lawmaker, historian, scientist, conqueror, emperor and finally as a prisoner, exile and overthrown at the Battle of Waterloo in 1815. The millennial patterns got changed: the external means of transforming world replaced by internal due to failure of promise, and disenfranchisement of faith. The Pilgrimage and quest of mankind for 'Liberty, Equality, Fraternity' has been internalized and golden age thought to be achieved by radical transformation of consciousness. The promise of revolution became deformed ideal and served as stark visual and

psychological metaphor for moral and social deformities of humanity in the Romantic literature. Therefore, the use of deformed bodies in the Romantic literature represents crippled nation, loss of identity, loss of integrity, and moral disfigurement. William Wordsworth in his poem Old Man Travelling stated:

While Glory seemed Betrayed...

and horror breathing from the silent ground (2018). There is tonal shift in narrative of the Great Britain's Romantic literature from optimism to pessimism due to morbid curiosity of wounding ideology of Napoleonic Wars to which Romantics witnessed. Wordsworth's poetry became gory description of heinous atrocities and brutality of French Revolution and Napoleonic Wars. The ending of wars was traumatic for victors as well as the vanquished. The war had been a costly affair between monetarily and in human lives. Much of the economic burden fell on the people in form of taxes thus increasing their stress, economic depression, unemployment and class unrest. The Napoleonic wars affected the lives of people in Britain directly and indirectly: Britain generated paranoid reaction of extended army from 40000 men in 1793 to 250000 in 1813 and supplemented 400000 mercenaries. Therefore, battlefield became home front against France. The principal poetical subjects were dismal picture of individuals from home front extended to battlefield. Oscar James stressed on Wordsworth's aesthetics in Guilt and Sorrow (1792) on disillusioned, distressed and obsessed reality as:

Disease and Famine, Agony and Fear... Dried up, despair, desolute and groans... To Loathsome Vaults... Hope died and Fear in agony was lost (1926; 298). Paul Stock stated, "Romanticism both defines and is defined by the complex legacy of Napoleon" (20). The myth of French Revolution for humanitarian purpose soon converted into Reign of Terror with the existence of French Republic. Maximilian Robespierre antagonism to clerical sentiment resulted in Thermidorian Reaction of Execution and Massacre. Bertrand Barere in 1793 exclaimed, "Let's make terror the order of the day" (Yon 1958). The ideology of Enlightenment provides the leaders of Reign of Terror the Social Contract theories about the

structure of government and its role. Jean Jacques Rousseau stressed that each individual is born with civil and natural rights and it is the responsibility of government to protect general will. Robespierre assumed that newly born French Republic would result in establishing general will but the leaders of revolt were expelled. Voltaire gave warnings against Catholic dogmas and the ways of Christianity, "Every individual who persecutes a man, his brother because he is not of his opinion is a monster" (Woolf 1924). The absolute monarchy of Louis XIV collapsed within three years of revolution. The Reign of Terror is marked by rejection of long held religious authority of doctrine of Divine Right, hierarchical system, intolerant influence of aristocracy and clergy. The powers of church were taken away and granted to state in 1789, majority of priests were killed and forced to leave. The new radical leaders tried to control on the de-Christianization movement as an open fear for catholic population of France. Wordsworth in 1793 wrote letters to the Bishop of Llandoff in which he declared his disillusionment for utopian ideals of French Revolution. In Ode: Intimation of Immortality (1807) he showed the second view of French Revolution fearful and painful truth:

Wither is fled the visionary Gleam?

Where it is now, the glory and the dream (2006; 21). The term fear and loathing in Romantic literature have different meanings to derive out depending upon the historical and literary context. The political climate of fear and sense of loathing for violence grappled the themes of social breakdown, tyranny, and individual vulnerability in the Romantic literature. Thus, Romantic period saw a deep exploration of sublime; a concept that involved feeling of awe, terror and overwhelming grandeur. Edmund Burke's A Philosophical Inquiry into the Origin of Our Ideas of the Sublime and Beautiful (1759) influenced the Romantic movement in connection of sublime to feelings of fear and danger. The terrors, miseries, regrets and lassitude have been infused in flux of experience and in memory of crippled nation left nothing but neurotic anxiety and disintegration psyche of grief and pain instead of promised joy for peace and order. The dual perception of French Revolution as 'Myth vs. Reign of Terror' and

Napoleon as 'Hero vs. Tyrant' became hallmark in Romantic literature.

Samuel Taylor Coleridge (1772-1834) is a reformist, revolutionary and reactionary to Napoleon as a heroic figure for upbringing of peace and democratic form of government. Due to ghastlier workings of war, he sought an escape into the world of mysterium magnum, astrology, mesmerism and magic. His involvement with Robert Southey, William Byron and William Gilbert manifested his mind for prognostication and Antiquarian talisman. From 1794 to onwards he turned from radicalism to apostasy passing from manic melancholia of witnessing onslaught on battlefield of tears and fears war brought on home ground. In *Fire, Famine and Slaughter* (1798) he expressed:

The man has bled... Their children faint for bread,
with bones and skulls, I made a rattle... Starving the
Other. (2000; 355)

In Christian mythology apostasy means to indulge in sin therefore Coleridge dwell in realm of horrified experiences to create things beyond understanding of human knowledge, power, explanation and reason. The *Rime of Ancient Mariner* (1798) was inspired by George Shelvocke's *A Voyage Round the World by way of Great South Sea* (1726) and Paracelsus Hermetic philosophy for the notion of curses. Therefore, in *The Rime of Ancient Mariner* Coleridge's Mariner showed affinity with culture of mesmerism and magic from beginning with 'Fear of Curses'.

The crew on ship blamed Mariner for bringing Supernatural Curse.

And I had done hellish thing,

For all averred, I had killed the bird (42).

The Gothic narrative addressed here to unseen, unknown and unacknowledged aspects of human existence. Coleridge's shifting of Gothic tale from traditional castles, monasteries, dungeons to a British ship sailing to Arctic which becomes a ghost ship was innovative. The arrival of Albatross is a welcome sign in Arctic region symbolizes good omen of Christian soul which miraculously steers the ship. The entire narrative is framed within wedding to show unity of two opposites poles of existence mind and culture, evil and good conceived in Coleridge's philosophy for instruction *Natura Naturata*. The shooting of the Albatross becomes apostasy for fall of man. The skull

of Albatross hung around his neck as a curse for sin and whole nature protested in horror. The Sun was flecked with bars, the stars were dim, the horned Moon, the rotting sea, air is cut and water is awful red. The Mariner is like a person who walks alone on a road, "doth walk in fear and dread" like, "a frightful fiend close behind him" (66). He spotted Specter-Bark mistakenly identified it as ship that might aid them. Due to lost voice Mariner bites his arm and drinks his own blood and became milestone in Gothic history for freakishness, "I bit my arm, I sucked the blood" (48). An indescribable feeling of terror reached to emotional pinnacle through self-abased sublimity. The Mariner deeply loathed his condition which was agonizing punishment surpassing physical, psychological and spiritual anguish. He received the blessings and divine revelation not by reason but by sensuous understanding of nature and chain of casualty linking to naturalism. By the end Mariner remains cursed by the pathological need to retell his tale and it is clear long - internalized spell is not lifted. Therefore, Coleridge depicted the seeds of 'Fear of Existential Isolation, Fear of Supernaturalism and Fear of Retribution' to illustrate fractured self and tortured reality.

That agony returns:

And till my ghastly tale is old (72).

William Blake (1757-1827) is a visionary poet-prophet, engraver, artist, illuminated printer whose work reflected magic, mysticism and occult under the influence of Jacob Boheme. In *Marriage of Heaven and Hell* (1794) Blake defined his own mythological world one that reinforced dislike, mistrust and 'Fear of Orthodoxies' of his time. He joined the new church of Emanuel Swedenborg in 1789 in which truth came from personal revelations not from priestly academics and arguments. Swedenborg subscribed Blake to Kabbalistic belief of Jewish mysticism and esotericism. The teachings set to explain relation between God, infinite mysterious and finite universe. Blake infused mesmerism and magical tricks in his work learnt from Richard Cosway and Count Cagliostro. Both of them sought alchemical transmutation of base metal into gold but believe that true transformation meant the release of illuminated soul from darkness. Therefore, Blake's poetry is dense and multi-layered expressed wide range of emotions. In *The Marriage of Heaven and Hell* (1790) he stated,

Without contraries is no progression.

Attraction and repulsion, reason and energy, love and hate,

are necessary to human existence (131).

Blake represented theological manifesto in form of dualism or binaries between heaven and hell, light and dark, good and evil, anarchy and order, humiliation and pride, attraction and repulsion and love and hate. The binaries formed symbiotic Theory of Cycles: one can't exist without other. He created supernatural machinery in the description of Angels, Devils, Heaven, Hell, Prophet Isaiah and Ezekiel, "I have always found that Angels have the Vanity to speak of themselves as the only wise. This they do with confident insolence is sprouting from systematic reasoning" (89). Like Devil the Romantics are rebel and Blake is of the opinion that Angels are church figures and religious conservatives who wish to control the reasons of individuals. Devils are classical liberals and Romantics who seek to liberate humanity from false constructions of social orders of church and system. He believed religious authorities misinterpreted the truth of heaven and hell. He showed us the second side of the coin in his, honest indignation is the voice of God, "I care not for consequences but wrote". He is anti-establishment radical, compared printing press as Devil's work or a house in hell to provide reason and truth to people in the presence of The Licensing Act (1737). Same is true for Greek mythology, Prometheus stole fire defies God giving it to humanity and remained in everlasting torment for crime he committed. The Romantics are Prometheans of humanity who raised voices for liberty of their fellow beings, "O horrible, O dreadful state! consider the hot burning Dungeon... Going in such career" (110). Like in Marlowe's Dr. Faustus and Goethe's Faust good and bad sides appeared again to give warnings for redemption so Blake created same therapy of hell as a concept of 'Fearsome and Loathsome' place. The hell might look like full of torment but actually a place where freethinkers, writers, intellects, reformers and revolutionaries can delight and revel in full experience of existence. No one have neither experienced hell or heaven it is about thinking state of mind, "the mind is its own place and in itself can make a heaven of hell a hell of heaven" (Milton 49). Blake mocks at Great Britain as a dungeon and unreal place to live, in his poem

Europe: A Prophecy (1794) due to war of ideologies for territorial gain and brought apocalyptic frenzy of madness in its violence. The heaven is converted into hell as:

And in the vineyard of Red France appeared, The light of his Fury...

The Furious Terrors flew around (20).

In his seminal work, Songs of Innocence and of Experience he saw 'Fear as Consequence of Societal Corruption and Control'. The Chimney Sweeper powerfully depicts the fear and misery of child labor by a pervasive dread of, "weep, weep". He saw fear as a product of oppressive system therefore his work depicts the destructive consequences of negative emotions. Many of his poems portrayed deep sense of disillusionment and a sense of loathing for corrupting forces that destroy innocence. His poems like A Poison Tree and Holy Thursday expressed strong aversion for societal and religious corruption. For him confronting the contrary states are essential to achieve a higher state of being and understanding.

Lord Gordon Byron (1788-1824) was a social revolutionary and radical thinker resembled William Blake in his condemnation of philistinism, and hypocrisy of monarchy. He became the crusader for the emancipation of the commonality when he visited Greece to support the struggle of people against despotic rulers. He idolizes Napoleon Bonaparte from his childhood: he was only one year old all begin and 27 years old when all ended. He formed Napoleonic cult of dynamic man of destiny in his anti-heroes for implication of tragic horror. The appreciation of Napoleons' regime is found in characteristic of criminal deed that can be seen in his lack of remorse. The dramatic poem Manfred (1817) is a closet drama set in Gothic castle in which anti-hero Manfred is haunted by his own sense of guilt for destroying Astrate a girl he loves in the past, "We are the fools of time and terror... Loathing our life, and dreading still to die" (64). The uplifted thought of his rejection of penitence to protect himself accounts for his sense of pride and heroic dimension parallel to Satan of Paradise Lost. To the Abbot he says, "The innate tortures of that deep despair. which is remorse without the fear of hell. Would make a hell of heaven" (66). Manfred's traumatic experience of guilt and remorse makes him ask for forgetfulness instead of forgiveness in this way his egoism makes him feel

superior in mental power to the average man. He attempted to commit suicide challenges the divine retribution. Byron invokes element of supernaturalism in six spirits of the universe and a seventh who foretells Manfred's personal destiny. The Spirits offered him, kingdom, and sway, and strength, and length of the days, but are unable to provide what he is looking for forgetfulness about the past (Byron 121). Byron showed us that Magic and Supernatural has its bound it cannot undo what has passed. He rejected the claims of witches, the Spirits of the universe, the forces of Arimanes and Nemesis, the solace of the nature and finally the Abbot. Manfred symbolizes chutzpah (extreme sense of self-confidence or audacity) and hubris in both cases; firstly, when he asked for forgetfulness and secondly when he discarded the spiritual authorities, "Patient and Patience! Hence the world was made... I am not thine order" (162). Manfred is infused with Promethean Spark to defy any external authority. To the Spirits he replied, "The mind, the spirit, the Promethean Spark... And shall not yield to yours, though cooped in clay" (139). Byron compared Manfred to Prometheus symbolizes Napoleon as defiant and revolutionary. Both of them are impatience to yearn limitless existence therefore invoked their tragedy. The 'Fear of Punishment and Fear of Retribution' did not overcome their egoism therefore both Napoleon and Manfred became rebel of their own types.

Elements of Romanticism affected writers in different ways to evoke uncanny and macabre. The French form of Romantic sensibility affected Victor Hugo (1802-1885) in a way he produced bleak picture of society in Hunchback of Notre - Dame (1831). Hugo voiced for abolition of capital punishment in Reign of Terror due to execution of thousands of people. Hugo's father Leopold Hugo was an officer in Napoleon's army so Hugo considered Napoleon as hero having electrifying spark. He witnessed the national political turbulence when Bourbon Monarchy was restored. He was champion of Radical Liberalism wanted freedom of press, social, institutional and economic reform for citizens. Hugo lived in exile because his dreams shattered due to Napoleon's fall. The concept of fear, terror and horror he presented in The Hunchback of the Notre - Dame aroused from personal, social and political devastation. It refers to the debilitated condition fire

has caused to The Notre Dame Cathedral in which it was ruined and condition of disrepair Hugo felt about. In 1790s many of the treasures including 500 statues were looted and destroyed in French Revolt. Cathedral was used as store house or as a place for anti- Catholic celebration. It became the place for Napoleon Coronation ceremony in 1804. The enthusiastic fame of Gothic tale produced by Hugo was enough for king Philippe to order the renovation and restoration in 1844. New techniques were added to original style but repair made cathedral worse, "who put the cold white panes in the place of those stained-glass windows... substituted... Gothic Alter" (131). Hugo describes Quasimodo as 'Object of Fear' for grotesque appearance of deformed body: hunchback with giant wart that covers his left eye. The people of Paris treated him with loath, disgust and cruelty rather to emphasized on pure soul confined in deformed body. His mother left him at gate of Cathedral picked up by Claude Frollo; Archdeacon. He became deaf due to ringing bell of cathedral and learnt the sign language just like creature of novel the Frankenstein. Hugo called an attention to the corruption of celibacy and religious deviation from holy conduct. Claude Frollo is the most disturbing representation of loathing in the novel representing how a clergy man born from repressed desires, religious fanaticism and intellectual arrogance. Another Gypsy character is Esmeralda as she becomes the object of lust and obsession for Claude Frollo to attain her like his temptation to create gold. Frollo orders Quasimodo to abduct Esmeralda being as faithful and loyal servant to master. Quasimodo attempted to seize her but his efforts are thwarted by Captain Phoebus and king's archers. Quasimodo is captured and brought to trial and sentenced to be whipped on pillory for two hours in public. Frollo instigates the malevolent crime, sets the trap and abandons him to suffer the consequence alone. Frollo consumed by jealousy and obsession secretly stabs Captain Phoebus during a meeting between Phoebus and Esmeralda. While she was innocent of the crime but due to Gypsy background she was seen as demonic and accused of witchcraft by court. Esmeralda who is victim and bearer of fear, 'Fear of Persecution and Accusation' sentence to death. Under torture, Esmeralda is coerced into false confession for Phoebus's murder. She was locked up in cell Frollo being a Priest visited her cell and offered

her to give herself to him or face death. Mathew Lewis (1775-1818) in *The Monk* (1796) presented the same aspects of religious horror. Ambrosio; the Monk committed rape of Antonia and murder Elvira to prevent her revealing from crime. The Nun Agens broke her vow of Celibacy gives birth to her child in imprisonment. Hugo and Lewis condemned hypocritical chastity of veil and oppression of church figures. The church and cathedral became the place in which beautiful women were enclosed, seduced and spoiled by clergy. The 'Fear of Priesthood' is focused in Anti-Catholic writings by both writers for the vows of sexual repression leading to diseased mind and bodies of church figures. In both texts the Monk and the Priest tempted to commit sin that led to transgression and loss of eternal salvation. Just like Agens loved rotten corpse of her child Emeraldal's deformed body is loved by Quasimodo. The *Hunchback of Notre Dame* and *The Monk* are both iconic Gothic novels of religious hypocrisy demonstrated the 'Fear and Loathing' for repressed unchecked passions which ultimately destroy the innocent object of desire. Both novels offered to judge the detrimental reality of 'Fear of Monster' perceives in normal bodies without pure souls and directed hearts.

The Romantic writers defined malaise of their time in variety of techniques to portray embattled self and malevolent forces in dichotomy of destruction and conservation, heaven and hell, exile and reunion, dejection and joy, order and anarchy, paradise lost and paradise regain. Due to intense sense of neurotic anxiety about fear of uncertainty and fear of insecurity Romantics fall into moments of melancholia projected and dramatized their sense of belonging to exotic, untamed and uncanny manifestation. The hermeneutics of representation presented enslaved and engulfed people with the authority of dark powers. The Romantic writers envisioned diverse literary techniques to create enigma of fear such as Occultism, Bohemianism, Kabbalism, Mesmerism, Esotericism, Witchcraft, Visionary Prophecies, Alchemical Jargons, Science based Myths, Gothic, Necromancy to combat inner conflict of self. Giordano Bruno stated, "Modern philosophy in first was astounding occurrence in history of mankind... as popular mythologies and theogonies proceeded science.... accepted by almost every part of intellectual

level" (209). Another way of creating fear in Romantic Literature is Gothic description as a way to expose troubling implications of 18th century in scientific discourse of vernacular canon. For many centuries Gothic Fiction provided writers multi-faceted faculty of imagination to address contemporary fears. With the arrival of technological changes, the nature of Gothic Fiction modified with time from one generation to another. In early Gothic novels Horace Walpole's, *The Castle of Otranto* (1764), Ann Radcliffe's *The Mysteries of Udolpho* (1794) the settings were exotic landscapes and remote timings. The action of texts culminated in desolate, dark and decayed crumbling castles, monasteries and church while the antagonists were tended to be corrupt celibacy and sex-crazed Monks and Nuns. Later in Victorian age the scene shifted to combat of body and mind exploring, mutating and decaying in respond to evolutionary scientific theories. Gothic Fiction has the ability to adapt to environmental issues therefore showed 'Fear of Darwinism'. The balance between faith and doubt was disturbed and question about the origin and destiny of humankind became watchword of the age. Alfred Lord Tennyson stated in *In Memoriam* (1850);

By faith, and faith alone, embrace,

Believing where we cannot prove; (2015; 9).

Charles Darwin in *Origin of Species* (1859) suggested that man is descended from tailed animal having common origin and developed a notion that human race is changeable and future is uncertain and unknown. Victorians took this reason as a ground for decaying and degenerated vision of human race in wider fields of society. The Theory of Degeneration was influential in 18th and 19th centuries shared by number of biologists, physicians, psychologist and criminologists like Immanuel Kant, Comte de Buffon, Johann Friedrich, Ceasre Lombroso and Max Nordau. The theory arouses particularly due to psychological negative impacts of urbanization and industrialization which were root cause for mental disorders, deformed states and declined physical health. The rapid progress in industrial, economic and political fields gave rise to criminal craving, feminist upheavals, sexual perversion, over-population, unemployment, poverty and class-oriented society. The depression and anxieties of era is presented in Gothic Literature in which characters

transmuted into ghosts, vampires, dracula, demons, monsters to symbolize displaced representation of what is unaware, unacknowledged, unacceptable and inaccessible in society.

The Strange Case of Dr Jekyll and Mr. Hyde (1886) is a degenerated discourse because Robert Louis Stevenson gave fictional identity to the emerging crisis of century. Stevenson asserted that 'Fear of Innate Beast' is to be purged in order to lay beyond animal instincts. In Victorian society duality of freak was taken as threatening and taken as, "the freak could be... male and female... human and animal at the same time" (Durbach 3). The 'Fear of Degeneration' is seen in Mr. Hyde," there is something wrong in his appearance, something displeasing... detestable... deformed. (5). Hyde symbolizes the animal instinct buried in human unconscious and brought forth by scientific experimentation of scientist Jekyll. Long before the identification of Hyde, he was supposed as creature who" had no face"(8). Faceless personality added anxiety of secrecy to his character which pointed towards unrecognizable identity as a sign of Othering for society. The concept of having no identity means one cannot be accountable for the wrong doings as a great danger to society. The description Stevenson penned down in the text for Hyde is "pale and dwarfish without any nameable malformation"(10). In this way he is displaced from normalcy towards Othering. Hyde is able to perceive second identity to manipulate others to move in society undetected which is an alarming situation for society to control, "Master Hyde... have black secrets" (11). However, Jekyll is responsible for black secrets of Hyde but cannot expose the reality for fear of consequences for his actions. He attempted to modify humanity and the outcome is reversing situation by creating animal nature of man, "haunting sense of unexpressed deformity" (17). Each person sees his own inner frightening states of past crimes when came in contact to Hyde. Dr Jekyll represents, "a cry of Victorian man from the depths of self-imposed underground" (Saposnik 721). He distorted reality and created evil to show deception and disguise in the world developed by science. Jekyll and Hyde showed conflict between Scientific urge and creativity under social pressure. Stevenson emphasized that Scientists had no Mastery over their experimentation therefore fall victim to their own creation destroying the notion

that science has tendency for good. Jekyll planned to live in extreme solitary state and proclaimed his friends to, "go my own dark way... brought on myself a punishment and danger that I cannot name"(23). He locked himself in study to accomplish his scientific endeavors to create Newness or Othering. His servant heard pain of crying, "him or it... crying night and day for some medicine cannot get to his mind"(29). After his transformation Utterson stated to Jekyll's servant as, "Your master is... seized... with both torture and deform the sufferer"(30) Both Jekyll and Hyde utilized each other as masks to hide. Judith Halberstam noted that, "Hyde hide within Jekyll; Jekyll is hidden the mask of Hyde and difference is crucial to staking out of their particular identities. Hyde is an eruption which disfigured and disappears Jekyll and Jekyll is reposition of order pushing him back into dark recesses of the self" (68). The creator and monster are interchangeable entities that symbolizes monstrosity or harm dwelling in inner strata of home and can be unleashed at any moment. Evil and good, normalcy and abnormality are contrary and compulsory elements to each other. Jekyll's quest for "separation of elements" into humanity and monstrosity witnessed that without conscience man is a barbarous brute no matter mechanically, scientifically and economically human race became modified and advanced, "evil...seemed natural and human...all human beings... led out of good and evil" (45). The renowned Italian criminologist Cesare Lombroso proposed Theory of Anthropology argued that born criminals could be identified by their features like Hyde's troglodytic appearance in Jekyll and Hyde's identification as criminal. Hyde is socially outcast while Jekyll is honorable person in society yet different facets of same person. The implication that criminality could lurk behind the mask of acceptable persona in society paves the way to see reality underneath as, 'Fear of Secrecy, Fear of Duality, Fear of Unnatural, and Fear of Moral Decay' in the novel. Mary Shelley's novel Frankenstein (1818) attracted theme of disability in monstrosity of creature with novels preoccupation of vision, visibility and blindness. In her own life she was baffled by grimmest appearance of mother's death at the time of her birth. She witnessed Fanny Imlay's her half-sister committed suicide after discovering that she was not William Godwin's daughter but one of the beloveds of Mary

Wollstonecraft. Her body was thrown nameless to pauper's grave and Godwin refused to claim her body. She also witnessed suicide of Harriet the first wife of Percy Bysshe Shelley. Mary Shelley gave birth for five times stillborn but not secured motherhood. She was not the legal wife of Percy Bysshe Shelley. Therefore, in Frankenstein she showed 'Fear of Lost Identity' as birth myth of Creature or Monster. Ellen Moers in *Literary Women* was the first who coined the term Female Gothic Genre written by female centered on the Romantic and Gothic traditions as original tone of novel Frankenstein. The female gothic genre converted a man into superman to break superhuman limitations to defy rules of society infringing God's realm. For her Frankenstein, "is abnormal, or Monstrous manifestation of child-parent tie to transform the standard of Romantic matter of infanticide and patricide into Phantasmagoria of nursery" (278). At the moment of birth, the Monster was innocent as a new born child and entirely benevolent. The Monster was defenseless as a human infant having blurred vision with confusion of senses and capacity of wonder. The Monster being as inexperienced yet incapable of interpreting the world with its meanings, significances and perceptions rejected by its maker Victor Frankenstein due to terrifying outlook. He neither gives Monster paternal love nor takes responsibility for sustenance not give it a name which caused lack of Identity. At the time of birth Monster is met with disgust and horror. He has no fault of his own yet deprived of all love, sympathy and companionship due to his outward appearance which made him outcast of society, "Was man, indeed, at once so powerful, so Virtuous, and magnificent, yet so vicious and base" (66).

Mary Shelley poses many questions on the part of creature and creator that who is truly human, inhuman and humanity's monsterdom in whole. The novel reveals the bitter fact that creator being as human is concealing a Monstrousness under his mask because he ignored his own invention, "man how ignorant art thou in thy pride of wisdom. Nothing is so painful to the human mind as a great and sudden change" (121). Monster weeps out in 'Fear of Humanity' after rejection and being thrown away. However, Monster still have longings to join human society and his brief interaction with Blind De Lacey becomes pivotal because blind character was excluded

from visual realm and blindness enables him to be sympathetic to Monster. The motive of blindness invokes aesthetic morality and gentleness of soul. However human society rejects those who are other regardless of beauty of soul so Monster is again rejected and beaten up by Felix mercilessly another human behaving monstrously for the charge of respect, love and affection Monster showed towards them. He has been abused and reviled by those people whom he trusted best despite of essential goodness he is hated and in return he can only hate mankind. "I am Fearless and therefore powerful" (139).

She encoded the doctrine of Separate Sphere theory in response of Victor to create a mate for Monster an Eve to comfort and embrace him. Awakened by the sense of conscience to do justice with monster he promised to create a female mate. He again gets terrified by the thoughts of sexually liberated female who will beget horrible progeny which will bring disaster to humanity. Mary Shelley exposes Victor's fear in many ways, firstly Victor is nervous to create an independent female will for revolutionary right to determine own existence, secondly, he is reluctant by the thought of Desire and opinion she will have, thirdly he is unwilling to create it for the desires and opinions make her uncontrollable, unmanageable, ungovernable and defiant. He imagines her ten thousand times Evilier than her mate therefore feels terrified by the vision of gigantic strength of female who can rape male easily he might choose. Therefore, Victor asserted male control over female body and mutilated the female mate of Monster symbolizes dominance and sovereignty over womanhood in patriarchal society, "Am I to be thought the only criminal when all human kind sinned against me? I the miserable and the abandoned, am an abortion, to be spurned at, and kicked, and trampled on. Even now my blood boils at the Recollection of this injustice" (198). Devon Hodges in her essay *Frankenstein and the Feminine Subversion of the Novel* noticed reversal of the roles of male authors by dubbing, "Mary Shelley own voice in male narratives to challenge the authority of the cultural order by individualism influenced by scientific revolt" (86). The spirit of science in Romantic period demonstrated the evil powers of self-identity and self-reliance teeming in individualism. The novel is profound cycle of fear and loathing such as fear of

own creation as a consequence and responsibility, society's fear of creature being othered, and Monster's fear of humanity being inhuman.

The "Fear of Napoleonic Wars" ever remained suspended in Britain because French Scientist Jean Rozier invented Hot Air Balloon in 1785 and crossed English Channel. Thus, 'Fear of Aerial Invasion' was dominant which shaped English politics and policies. The Count Dracula (1897) by Bram Stoker (1847-1912) is a monumental text to show 'Fear of Changing Traditional Roles of Women and Fear of Reverse Colonialism (Othering, Foreignness)'. Stoker followed the pattern of Invasion Literature popular in between 1871- 1918. Invasion Literature is a literary genre became popular after publishing The Battle of Dorking (1871) by George Tomkyns. The Count Dracula as Invasion Literature is a foreigner to English land migrated from Transylvania to feed on English blood, "our ways are not your ways" (23). Stoker emphasized on multiculturalism by inserting different nationalities Saxons, Magyar, Szekelys that symbolises collective consciousness of invasion and a threat to downfall of the British Empire. The Dracula is obsessed with blood sucking baptism to create sinister environment multiplying undead victims, "Blood is too precious thing... he glorifies of the Great race" (34). During 19th century scientists invented new ways of Theory of Spermatic Economy where semen was regarded as part of blood therefore symbolizes contamination of English race and racial decline. Victorian mentality believed in purity of blood and race while Dracula polluted it by seducing English ladies. The belief in English racial superiority was fundamental pillar of British imperialism. The 19th century witnessed the proliferation of scientific racism attempted to classify humanity into distinct hierarchical order of races. Carl Linnaeus, Johann Friedrich Blumenbach, Samuel George Morton, Joseph Arthur de Gobineau, Francis Galton and Robert Knox are prominent scientists contributed to intellectual philosophy of race and oppression. The period coincides with increased Atlantic Slave Trade through Triangular Trade to rationalize the power based on biological differences. It provided the moral and intellectual justification for extending British power across globe as White Man's Burden. The imperial colonialism of Europe increased from 35% to 85% between 1815-1914 and over 150 million

people were humiliated and oppressed around globe. Edward Said in Orientalism (1978) describes the ways of interaction between West and East as Occident and Orient. Orientalism is a political doctrine in which Orientalist made to feel only Occident has value and truth. West represents order, technology and history and it is the home of creators, masters and rulers. The western land is sacred and mythical while people of West are civilized, humanized and missionaries who imparted to East nothing but homelessness, emptiness, nothingness and darkness. West does not understand the ones who are not from it creating boundary between self and others with the mission to illumine and eliminate. The story of West becomes "age of crime" refers to Holocaust, Holodomor and responsible for genocide of millions of people around world who became victims of their ferocious treatment of territorialization and expansionism. They carry the seeds of disintegration, categorization and degradation towards which colonized experienced fear of insecurities and maladjustment they tried to loath. The Victorian mentality is a social phenomenon that can be best judged by Queen Victoria's statement in 1870, "let women be what God intended, a help mate for man, but with totally different duties and vocation" (Rappaport 125). She voiced for Separate Sphere theory for discrimination and keeping hedge between genders however she herself was Paradox of female ruler over world. One aspect of Victorian mentality is exemplified in Paul Broca's discovery that the average brain of a woman is weighed 140 gm less than male brain. The English society took this reason as a ground of Othering for enfranchisement of legal, social, political and economic rights of women. Women were treated as emotional and less intellectual rather than judgmental and rational. By 19th century, the age known as for Liberty, Equality and Fraternity still posed hypocritical plan in which women were not allowed to get education, having no rights to cast votes, own property and to take divorce. By 1880 Education Act was passed to make education compulsory for women. In 1918 women casted first time in history their votes and opened the gates of reform and economic equality for themselves. The society was becoming aware of the fact that their beliefs whether social, political and religious were no longer secure due to increase of knowledge creating fear for changing traditional roles

of women in history. In the novel, Dracula originating from backward East invades the heart of British Empire: London. Stoker brought the psyche of inversion of colonial dynamics. The Dracula being from distant land presented as monstrous 'other' taken as a threat to British identity, purity and order. Stoker showed 'Fear of Intellectual and Cultural Invasion' in the novel as Dracula studies English language, customs, law to exploit the target fully. This reflects the fear that colonized can learn the ways of colonizers and use that knowledge, representation and language as a tool against them.

A key anxiety of the Victorian era was the 'Fear of Degeneration' both racial and moral. Lucy is a Latin word means light of West, since Dracula is invading from East and targeted Lucy as West. The transformation of Lucy into vampire woman is a stark manifestation of this fear in conservative society. She provoked Arthur to kiss and her repressed sexual desire has been released which seen as danger and a potential to challenge and subvert Victorian values, "New Woman will introduce the idea that men and women should be allowed to see each other asleep before proposing or accepting" (125). The lines suggested that Victorian women ought to be progressive and economically independent. Lucy received four blood transfusions from Arthur Holmwood, Quincey Morris, John Seward and Abraham Van Helsing enjoying the status of New Woman. Arthur punished her by driving stake into her heart, "this undead... to loathe it" (233). She becomes undead because she remained no longer a Victorian Victim, seen as mannish, sexually threatening and unnatural by society. John Stuart Mill in *The Subjection of Women* (1869) stated, "The principle of demarcation between two sexes which regulates the legal subordination of one sex is highly wrong... It must be replaced by principle of perfect quality by acknowledging no power over other" (144). The novel appeared as testament to explore the collective cultural anxieties like 'Fear of Xenophobia, and Fear of Contamination'.

CONCLUSION:

The 'Rapture to Revulsion' spectrum is very apt way to describe the intense emotional range of fear and loathing explored by Romantic writers. Romantic Movement is the literary, intellectual and artistic movement inspired all Romantics to break tyrannical

bound and conformist notions that had kept in chains the human spirit for centuries. The pivotal percept of subjectivity, expressionism and individualism is found in bombastic variety of moods and techniques to capture the complexed scenario of age i.e., 'Fear of War, Fear of Territorialization, Fear of Invasion, Fear of Scientific Innovation, Fear of Imperialism, Fear of Feminism, Fear of Xenophobia, Fear of Orthodoxies and Fear of Doubt and Faith'. The Romanticism is an age of crisscross doctrines Pantheism VS. Atheism, Transcendentalism VS. Scientific Rationalism that aroused Pessimistic thought to view darker side of nature. The Romantics intertwined multiple narratives like Gothic, Science Fiction, Supernaturalism, Mysticism, Occultism, Degeneration to impart sublimity of imaginative style. Romantic literature became Romantic rehabilitation of obsessive behaviors, deformed bodies and paranoid illness to portray crumbling environment of age: Fear and Loathing.

REFERENCES:

- Aurelius, M. (2018). *Meditations*. CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform.
- Aurelius, M. (2018). *Meditations*. CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform.
- Bainbridge, S. (2016). *Romanticism and War*. Oxford University Press.
- Barfield, O. (1971). *What Coleridge Thought*. Wesleyan University Press.
- Blake, W. (2014). *The Marriage of Heaven and Hell*. CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform.
- Blake, W. (2015). *Europe A Prophecy*. CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform.
- Bloom, H. (1971). *The Visionary Company, A reading of English Romantic Poetry*. Cornell University Press.
- Boheme, J. (2022). *The Supersensual Life*. CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform.
- Bruno, G. (1998). *Cause, Principle and Unity: An Essay on Magic*. Cambridge University Press.
- Byron, G. (1847). *The Giaour, The poetical works of Lord Byron*. John Murray London.
- Byron, L. (2014). *Manfred*. CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform.
- Coleridge, S. T. (2000). *Fire, Famine and Slaughter*. Penguin Classics.

- Descartes, R. (1989). *The Passions of the Soul*. Hackett Publishing Company.
- Dubranch, N. (2010). *Spectacle of Deformity: Freak Shows and Modern British Culture*. Berkley University of California Print.
- Fuson, W. (2017). *The Historical Turn of Romantic-Era Disability Studies, or Frankenstein in the Dark: Frankenstein in the Dark*. ResearchGate Literature Compass.
- Halberstam, J. (1995). *Making Monsters: Marry Shelley Frankenstein: Gothic Horror and Technology of Monsters*. Durham: Duke UP.
- Higginson, W., T. (1955). *EPICETUS The Enchiridion*. The Library of Liberal Arts, New York.
- Hobbes, T. (2017). *Leviathan*. Penguin Classic.
- Hodges, D. (1983). *Frankenstein and The Feminine Subversion of The Novel*. Tulsa Studies in Women's Literature.
- Hogle, J. (2008). *Introduction: The Gothic in Western Culture*. Cambridge University Press. <https://www.wikipedia.org/>
- Hugo, V. (1891). *Hernani*. D.C. Heath.
- James, O. (1926). *Guilt and Sorrow: A Study in the Genesis of Wordsworth's Aesthetic*. *Modern Philology*, vol.23.
- Kaster, R. (2010). *Seneca: Anger, Mercy, Revenge*. *The Complete Works of Lucius Anneaus Seneca*. University of Chicago Press.
- Lewis, M. (1851). *The Monk*. Oxford University Press.
- Mill, J. S. (1869). *The Subjection of Women*. Longman London.
- Milton, J. (2016). *Paradise Lost*. CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform.
- Moers, M. (2014). *Literary Woman: F**k It: The Ultimate Spiritual Way*. Oxford University Press,
- Paul, R. (2007). *Ancient Mariner*. Famous Products, Pakistan.
- Poornima, M. D. (2015). *Can the Subaltern Speak? In Colonial Discourse and Post-Colonial Theory*. Pune Research International Journal in English.
- Rappaport, H. (2003). *Queen Victoria: A Biographical Companion*. CLIO Inc.
- Rousseau, J. J. (1706). *The Essential Writing of Jean Jacques Rousseau*. The Vintage Classic.
- Sartre, P., J. (2007). *Existentialism and Humanism*. Methuen Publishing Limited.
- Shelley, M. (1994). *Frankenstein*. Dover Publications Print.
- Spinoza, B. (2005). *Ethics*. Penguin Classic.
- Stevenson, R. L. (1991). *The Strange Case of Dr Jekyll and Mr Hyde*. Dover Publication New York.
- Stock, P. (2006). *Imposing on Napoleon: The Romantic Appropriation of Bonaparte*. *Journal of European Studies*.
- Stoker, B. (1897). *The Count Dracula*. Archibald Constable and Company U.K.
- Susan, F. (1976). *Poetic Form in Blake's Milton*. Princeton University Press.
- Taylor, T. (1818). *The Rhetoric, Poetic and Nicomachean Ethics*. A.J. Valpy, Tooke's Court.
- Tennyson, A; L. (2015). *In Memoriam*. Digireads.com.
- Tinker, B. (1940). *The Poetry of Matthew Arnold*. Oxford University Press.
- Wordsworth, W. (1850). *The Prelude*. Penguin Classics.
- Wordsworth, W. (2006). *Ode: Intimations of Immortality from Recollections of Early Childhood*. Kessinger publishing.
- Wordsworth, W. (2018). *Old Man Travelling*. Fingerprint! Publishing.